

October 31, 2025

<https://ijoabs.com/>
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

Impact of Beneficial Soil Bacteria, Growth Promoting Hormones, and Nutritional Solutions on Sugarcane Physiology, Cane Population, Yield and Economics

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Received Date: 31-Aug-2025

Accepted Date: 05-Sep-2025

Published Date: 31-Oct-2025

Abstract

To study the effects of nutrient solutions, growth promoting hormones and beneficial soil microbes on sugarcane physiology, cane population, yield and economics, field experiments were carried out at the Sugarcane Research Station, Cuddalore for three years, from 2022-2025. The studies were set up using a randomized block design and were duplicated three times using eight different treatments viz., T₁- control, T₂- soil application of azophos @ 15kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, T₃- T₂ + foliar spray of nutrient solution along NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP, T₄-T₂ + foliar spray of nutrient solution along with kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP, T₅-foliar spray of nutrient solution and kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP, T₆-T₂+ foliar spray of nutrient solution and kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP, T₇-foliar spray of nutrient solution along NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP and T₈ - foliar spray of nutrient solution along with kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP. Pooled data of three years study indicated that different treatments with plant growth regulators had significant effect on growth, yield and quality parameters of sugarcane. These experiments showed that the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP resulted in significantly higher millable cane populations of 1.19 ('000/ha) in plant crops and 1.10 ('000/ha) in ratoon crops, leaf area index of 6.82 and 6.45 in plant and ratoon crops, total chlorophyll content of 4.82 mg/g and 4.24 mg/g in plant and ratoon crops respectively, cane yield in plant (132 t/ha) and ratoon cane (129 t/ha). Both Azophos biofertilizer and nutrient solution along with NAA hormone can be valuable tools for improving sugarcane yield and quality. Their combined application can lead to enhanced nutrient uptake, better root development, increased cane thickness, and ultimately, higher yields and sugar content.

Keywords: Azophos biofertilizer, nutrient solution, NAA hormone, sugarcane, ratoon crop

Introduction

India is the world's second-largest producer of sugarcane and sugar, accounting for 15% and 25% of worldwide production, respectively, behind Brazil (Mohan and Kanaujia 2017). All over the world, sugarcane (*Saccharum* spp. hybrid complex), a C₄ plant, is the most effective at transforming chemical and physical energy (solar energy, carbon dioxide, and water) into biological energy (sucrose), meeting 80% of the demand for sugar. In addition, India consumes 24.85 million tons of sugar annually, making it the world's largest consumer of the commodity. By 2050, the nation would need 48 million tons of sugar, up

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from 24.85 million tonnes currently. The crop needs a greater amount of nutrients. 208 kilograms of nitrogen, 53 kg of phosphorus, 280 kg of potassium, 30 kg of sulphur, 3.4 kg of iron, 1.2 kg of manganese, and 0.6 kg of copper are removed from the soil by an average sugarcane crop that produces 100 t/ha of economical biomass. To maintain production, these depleted nutrients must be restored. For the best, most economical, and most sustainable yield, a significant amount of chemical sources of these nutrients—70–400 kg/ha N, 27–74 kg/ha P, and 25–141 kg/ha K—have been suggested. These sources depend on the soil, crop type, and other agroclimatic factors (Anonymous 2013). Crops absorb nutrients from organic debris after microbes mineralize them, as well as nutrients that are already present in the seed piece, through biological fixation, etc., and particularly nitrogen from chemical fertilizers (Vitti et al., 2007). Either chemical fertilizers are used to supply more nutrients, or physical, chemical, or biological activities that alter the physicochemical characteristics of the soil make nutrients that are already readily available. In the early phases of plant development, nitrogen from chemical fertilizers only made up 40% of the total nitrogen in the cane; when the plant reaches maturity, this percentage drops to about 10% at harvest. In the first ratoon, nitrogen fertilizer is applied more efficiently for crop nutrition, accounting for up to 70% of total nitrogen in the early stages of development and thereafter declining throughout the cycle to reach about 30% at harvest (Franco *et al.*, 2011). According to Baldani *et al.* (1997), this process appears to involve both endophytic and rhizospheric diazotrophs. It would appear dishonest to prescribe just chemical fertilizers for the sugarcane crop since plants only absorb 40% of their nitrogen from chemical sources. In addition to improving sugarcane growth, the use of biofertilizers in conjunction with chemical fertilizers decreases cultivation costs, reliance on chemical fertilizers, pollution, and degradation of soil health. Utilizing natural resources is a significant step towards economic success for a nation like India, since the use of chemical fertilizers for crop production is costly due to limited supply and environmental pollution issues. According to Sabah *et al.* (2021) and Hirayama and Mochida (2022), plant growth regulators are a broad class of biomolecules that control development, growth, nutrient acquisition and allocation, and molecular and physiological crop responses, hence facilitating plant adaptation to environmental conditions. Numerous studies also showed that GA₃ influenced sucrose phosphosynthase activity (Iqbal *et al.*, 2011) and stimulated sink tissue growth, which increased sugarcane assimilation (Chandra *et al.*, 2015; Verma *et al.*, 2019). Endogenous auxins, such as indole-3-butyric acid (IBA), phenoxycetic acid (PAA), and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), which are produced from L-tryptophan and chorismate, the byproduct of the shikimate pathway, are crucial for cellular metabolism (Ljung 2013). According to Asgher *et al.* (2015), these auxins alter the patterns of gene expression in plants, which promotes growth and development. It is thought that several genes are involved in IAA production in the apical meristems of root cells, which are organs with active cell division and have high auxin concentrations (Ljung 2013). Since high atmospheric CO₂ concentrations increase the photosynthetic rate and, in turn, the production of photosynthates, auxins have a favorable impact on the regulation of stomatal opening and shutting (Snaith and Mansfield 1984). Chlorophyll and carotenoids are biosynthesised by CKs, which also directly contribute to chloroplast formation. (Cheminant *et al.*, 2011; Cortleven and Schmölling 2015) Carotenoids shield plastids from photooxidative damage. Carotenoids also have direct and indirect impacts on photosynthesis since they are linked to PSII chlorophyll a/b binding proteins and ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (Rubisco) activity (Iqbal *et al.*, 2011; Brenner and Schmölling 2012). Using 6-benzylamino-purine (BA) exogenously raises the electron transport rate (ETR), according to Yang *et al.* (2018). This study set out to assess how exogenous plant growth regulators applied topically affected sugarcane's photosynthesis, sugar and stalk yields, and antioxidant enzyme regulation. The main hypothesis of this study is that by stimulating the enzymes phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase (PEP-case; EC:4.1.1.31), Rubisco, and antioxidant enzymes involved in ROS scavenging, the application of plant growth regulators like Auxin (IAA), CKs (zeatin), and GAs (GA₃) to sugarcane will increase the photosynthetic rate and improve sugarcane yield, raw material quality, biometric parameters, and biomass production. Our current focus as scientists is on creating alternative technologies that will reduce reliance on chemical fertilizers and promote widespread adoption of biofertilizers by farming communities. Tropical and subtropical crops like sugarcane (*Saccharum* spp.) generate a lot of biomass and need significant water and nutrient inputs to reach their full potential. The objective of this field study was to evaluate the impact of PGRs, biofertilizers, and nutrient solutions on sugarcane germination, growth, yield, and juice quality when these facts were taken into consideration.

Material and methods

A field study was carried out in 2022–2025 at the Sugarcane Research Station in Cuddalore, Tamil Nadu. Sand clay loam constituted the soil at the trial site. Three replications of the experiment were set up in a randomized block design. CoC 13339 was chosen as the test variety. When the plants were planted, Azophos biofertilizers were applied in furrows as a base. Hand weeding, earthing up, trash twist propping, and other agronomic techniques were all done in accordance with the guidelines. Eight treatment combinations were used in the research viz., T₁- control, T₂- soil application of azophos @ 15kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, T₃- T₂ + foliar spray of nutrient solution along @ 30th DAP, T₄-T₂ + foliar spray of nutrient solution along with kinetin 50ppm @30th DAP, T₅- foliar spray of nutrient solution and kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP, T₆ - T₂+ foliar spray of nutrient solution and kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP, T₇ - foliar spray of nutrient solution @30th DAP and T₈ - foliar spray of nutrient solution along with kinetin 50ppm @ 30th DAP. All treatments were added on top of each plot at the start of the ratoon. All treatments had three intercultural operations (hoeing) and six irrigations in total. During the crop growth phase, growth data such as the germination percentage at 30 DAP and the tiller population following spraying at 180 DAP were noted. At harvest, physiological parameters like leaf area index and total chlorophyll, yield-attributable factors such as the length of the cane and the quantity of millable cane were noted. After removing the leaves and detopping, the yield of the cane was measured. The findings of statistical analysis of the collected data were compared.

Results and Discussion

Germination (%)

Germination was recorded at 30 days after planting and expressed in % and presented in Figure 1 and Table 1. At 30 DAP, significant differences were not observed due to different treatments. However, planting of setts after soil application of Azophos @ 15kg/ha recorded highest per cent germination of 82.58 % and 83.8% in pooled data of plant crop and ratoon crop respectively. At 30 days, planting of setts after the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP recorded significantly higher per cent germination as compared to other treatments. Conventional bud sett planting recorded significantly lowest per cent germination of 76.78 in ratoon crop. According to Patnaik and Nayak (2020), soaking setts in a solution of 100 ppm ethrel overnight and then administering a gibberellic acid solution superficially can enhance germination, subsequent growth, and sugarcane and sugar productivity.

Tiller population ('000/ha)

Number of tillers at 180 days after planting the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP recorded significantly a greater number of tiller population (1,67,000/ha and 1,68,000/ha) in plant crop and ratoon crop respectively as compared to other treatments in Figure 2 and Table 1. Planting of setts without treatments were recorded significantly lower number of tillers/ha (1,19,000/ha and 1,26,000/ha) in plant and ratoon crop respectively. In contrast to the control, the results of Rai *et al.* (2017) showed that phasic gibberellic acid administration increased the number of shoots. This resulted from a notable reduction in shoot mortality in the case of sugarcane planted traditionally. Applying GA₃ resulted in the establishment of a strong root system, which must have coordinated the absorption of water and mineral nutrients needed to promote the growth of the shoots. According to Gerardo *et al.* (2024), the use of biofertilizers to boost sugarcane biomass was linked to more tillering as opposed to higher stalk diameter or height.

Number of millable canes/ha

Significant differences were observed in number of millable canes due to application of different plant growth regulators (Figure 3 and Table1). Significantly higher number of millable canes of 1,19,000/ha and 1,10,000/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively were recorded by the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP. Conventional budded sett planting recorded significantly lower number of millable canes (92,000/ha

and 97,000/ha) in both plant and ratoon crop respectively. These results are consistent with Cong Truc Nguyen *et al.* (2019) findings.

Physiological parameters

Leaf area Index

Leaf area index was measured at harvest and data are presented in Figure 4 and Table 1. Significantly higher leaf area index of 6.82 and 6.45 in plant and ratoon crop respectively were recorded by the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP. Conventional budded sett planting recorded significantly lower leaf area of index (4.72 and 4.96) in both plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Total chlorophyll content (mg/g)

Leaf area index was measured at harvest and data are presented in Figure 5 and Table 1. Significantly higher total chlorophyll content (4.82 mg/g and 4.24 mg/g) in plant and ratoon crop respectively were recorded by the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP. Conventional budded sett planting recorded significantly lower total chlorophyll content (1.87 mg/g and 1.95 mg/g) in both plant and ratoon crop respectively. Moreover, Auxin, GAs, and strigolactones have an impact on photosynthesis and are crucial in lowering the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which may damaging the mechanism of photosynthesis (Müller *et al.*, 2021).

Yield parameters

Length of Cane (cm)

Length of the millable cane was measured at harvest in cm and data are presented in Figure 6 and Table 1. Significantly longest canes were recorded by the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP (282 cm and 280 cm) in plant and ratoon crop respectively. Conventional bud sett planting recorded significantly lowest length of millable cane (211 cm and 215 cm) in plant and ratoon crop respectively at harvest. Through the high concentration of IAA, which stimulated cell elongation and gene expression regulation, the initial application made during the vegetative stage of sugarcane increased stalk productivity and, as a result, sugar production (Tuan *et al.*, 2019).

Single cane weight (kg/plant)

Single cane weight was computed treatment wise. Single cane did not much varied significantly due to different treatments but highest single cane weight (2.25kg/plant and 2.20 kg/plant) in both plant and ratoon crop respectively (Figure 7 and Table 1) was recorded with T₃ treatment i.e the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th days after planting. Praharaj *et al.* (2016) also observed similar findings.

Cane yield (t/ha)

Cane yield (t/ha) Cane yield was recorded at harvest and presented in Figure 8 and Table 1. Significantly highest cane yield (132.0 t/ha and 129.0 t/ha) in plant and ratoon crop respectively was recorded by the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th DAP. Conventional budded sett planting recorded lowest cane yield of 119.0 t/ha and 116.0 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. In comparison to the traditional way of sugarcane planting, the cane yield attained with the application of growth-promoting hormones in all treatments was much higher. The findings from Praharaj *et al.* (2016) support the results. Ghodke *et al.*, 2022 has been found that foliar application of Gibberellic Acid (GA₃) + Six Benzylaminopurine (Six BA) 40 ppm each with 1% 19:19:19 + 0.25% chelated micronutrient + 0.5% Silicon with the general recommended dose of fertilizer (FYM 25 t ha⁻¹, 340:170:170 N, P₂O₅ and K₂O kg ha⁻¹) was advantageous for boosting sugarcane and commercial cane yield. During both study years, the highest cane yield produced by applying a soil test-

based recommended dose of fertilizer (RDF) + 25% N through pressmud + zinc sulfate was 38.3 and 37.4% greater than RDF (Sow *et al.*, 2025).

Conclusion

In conclusion the studies on use of biofertilizer, nutrient solution along with plant growth regulators (PGRs) for enhanced yield and quality of sugarcane conducted at Sugarcane Research Station, Cuddalore during 2022-2025 season revealed that the soil application of azophos @ 15 kg/ha + sugarcane booster recommended dose, foliar spray of nutrient solution and NAA 40 ppm @ 30th days after planting enhance the germination, tiller population and there by cane yield (132 t/ha and 129 t/ha) in both plant and ratoon crop respectively as compared to the conventional planting.

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Figure 1: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on germination (%) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

Figure 2: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on tiller population ('000/ha) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

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Figure 3: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on millable cane population (‘000/ha) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

Figure 4: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on leaf area index in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

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Figure 5: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on total chlorophyll (mg/g) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

Figure 6: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on cane length (cm) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

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Figure 7: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on single cane weight (kg/plant) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

Figure 8: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on cane yield (t/ha) in sugarcane plant crop (pooled data)

Table 1: Effect of beneficial soil bacteria, growth promoting hormones, and nutritional solutions on growth, physiology and yield parameters of ratoon crop in sugarcane

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Treatments	Establishment (%)	Tiller population ('000/ha)	Millable cane population ('000/ha)	Leaf Area Index	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g)	Cane length (cm)	Single cane weight (kg/plant)	Cane yield (t/ha)
T ₁	76.78	1.26	0.97	4.96	1.95	215.00	1.12	116.03
T ₂	82.20	1.56	1.03	5.98	3.22	255.01	2.15	125.00
T ₃	83.80	1.68	1.10	6.45	4.24	280.17	2.20	129.00
T ₄	78.95	1.48	1.01	5.42	3.17	241.10	1.32	122.00
T ₅	77.30	1.43	1.00	5.32	3.11	245.05	1.29	120.45
T ₆	81.22	1.53	1.02	5.62	3.21	265.00	1.45	124.42
T ₇	78.56	1.49	1.04	5.45	3.18	248.75	1.35	120.33
T ₈	77.30	1.32	1.02	5.27	3.07	239.00	1.28	121.00
SE (d)	1.99	0.02	0.02	0.14	0.08	5.37	0.07	1.20
CD	4.28	0.05	0.04	0.30	0.18	11.52	0.17	4.20